

**АНАЛИЗ МИРОВОГО ОПЫТА МАРКЕТИНГОВЫХ СТРАТЕГИЙ В ПОВЫШЕНИИ
ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ АКЦИОНЕРНЫХ ОБЩЕСТВ****Эркинов Ш.Б.**

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**ANALYSIS OF WORLD EXPERIENCE OF MARKETING STRATEGIES IN INCREASING THE
EFFICIENCY OF JOINT STOCK COMPANIES****Erkinov Sh.**

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Аннотация

В статье проведен всесторонний анализ мирового опыта применения маркетинговых стратегий для повышения эффективности деятельности акционерных обществ. Особое внимание уделяется инновационным подходам к сегментации рынка, позиционированию, формированию комплекса маркетинг-микс, а также использованию современных цифровых инструментов. Автором проанализирован наиболее значимые факторы, определяющие эффективность маркетинговых стратегий, такие как ориентация на потребителя, гибкость, интеграция со стратегией развития компании и эффективная реализация. На основе проведенного исследования сформулированы практические рекомендации по адаптации зарубежного опыта маркетинговых стратегий.

Abstract

The article provides a comprehensive analysis of global experience in applying marketing strategies to improve the efficiency of joint-stock companies. Particular attention is paid to innovative approaches to market segmentation, positioning, the formation of a marketing mix, as well as the use of modern digital tools. The author analyzed the most significant factors that determine the effectiveness of marketing strategies, such as customer focus, flexibility, integration with the company's development strategy and effective implementation. Based on the conducted research, practical recommendations have been formulated for adapting foreign experience in marketing strategies.

Ключевые слова: мировой опыт, маркетинговая стратегия, эффективность, акционерное общество.

Keywords: world experience, marketing strategy, efficiency, joint-stock company.

Introduction.

Marketing strategy is the definition of those markets that a firm chooses as the target of its marketing activities and the ways in which advantages in these markets will be created and achieved¹. A marketing strategy defines target markets, areas of development and, in general terms, what must be done to create and maintain a competitive position consistent with the overall corporate strategy in those target markets.

In modern conditions, internationalization and globalization of the world economy determine the process of companies entering the foreign market, which

helps improve the efficiency of joint-stock companies². Therefore, it is relevant to consider the characteristics of marketing strategies in various markets, the degree of centralization of these strategies and their exposure to economic globalization processes.

Theoretical aspects of research.

Global experience in marketing strategies covers a wide range of approaches that companies use to promote their products and services. Here are some examples of successful marketing strategies that have been widely used in global practice:

¹Easey, M. Fashion Marketing. 3rd ed. / M. Easey. - Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell, 2009. - 278 p.

²Transnational corporations [Electronic resource] // United Nations Conference on Trade and Development. - Mode of access:

[http://unctad.org/en/Pages/DIAE/Transnational-corporations-\(TNC\).aspx](http://unctad.org/en/Pages/DIAE/Transnational-corporations-(TNC).aspx).

Table 1.

World experience of successful marketing strategies³

Internet Marketing:	With the development of the Internet and social media, companies began to actively use online channels to promote their products. This includes website creation, content marketing, social media advertising, and e-commerce.
Affiliate Marketing:	Companies may collaborate with other firms or influencers to promote their products. For example, partnering with a popular blogger or collaborating with another company to create joint products.
Development of a unique brand:	Creating and promoting a unique brand helps companies stand out in the market and attract the attention of consumers. This includes developing a logo, slogan, packaging and other branding elements.
Advertising on television and radio:	Traditional media channels such as television and radio are still effective means of mass advertising. Companies post commercials and audio ads to reach a wide audience.
Public Relations:	Public relations help companies establish a positive image and build trust among consumers. This can be achieved through media briefings, press releases, participation in charity events and other forms of public relations.
Using data and analytics: campaigns	Modern marketing strategies are increasingly based on data analysis and the use of analytics tools to understand consumer behavior and determine the effectiveness of advertising
Influencer Marketing:	Popular social media influencers can be used to promote products and services. This could be in the form of sponsored posts, reviews, or product mentions in their content.

It is important to note that the effectiveness of marketing strategies may vary depending on the specific industry, target audience and other factors. When developing a marketing strategy, a company should

take into account the unique characteristics of its business and approach the choice of strategies taking into account the specific situation.

The following are a few basic marketing strategies that are widely used in global experience:

Table 2.

Basic marketing strategies⁴

Segmented Marketing:	Companies divide the market into separate segments and develop specific marketing strategies for each segment. This allows you to more accurately target the needs and preferences of specific consumer groups.
Differentiated Marketing:	In this strategy, companies develop different marketing strategies for different market segments. They create unique products, services and communication approaches to meet the different needs and preferences of each segment.
Mass Marketing:	In this strategy, companies target a wide audience and strive to achieve maximum market coverage. They develop versatile products and marketing communications that attract a large number of consumers.
«Low Price» Marketing Strategy:	Companies focus on providing goods and services at low prices to attract price-sensitive consumers. This strategy is usually based on achieving high sales volume and cost savings.
Marketing strategy «high quality»:	Companies focus on creating high quality products or services and highlight their superiority to consumers. This strategy is based on creating a prestigious and premium brand image.
Marketing strategy «innovation»:	Companies strive to stay ahead of the competition by developing innovative products and services. They actively invest in research and development to offer unique and cutting-edge solutions.
Marketing strategy «environmental responsibility»:	Companies are emphasizing environmental sustainability and responsibility in their marketing efforts. They may emphasize environmentally friendly products, sustainable production methods, or a social responsibility program.
Social Media Marketing Strategy:	Companies actively use social media platforms to attract and interact with audiences. They create content, launch advertising campaigns and build communities around their brands.

³Prepared by the author.

⁴Prepared by the author.

These are just a few examples of marketing strategies that are used worldwide. Companies can combine different approaches and tailor them to their unique needs and goals.

Research methodology.

Analysis of marketing strategy is an important tool for increasing the efficiency of joint-stock companies. Marketing strategy includes developing goals, identifying target audiences, choosing market positioning, defining marketing mixes (product, price, promotion, distribution) and developing appropriate tactics.

Marketing strategy analysis is useful in the following aspects⁵

Name	Definition
Defining goals and positioning:	Analyzing your marketing strategy will help you define clear and measurable goals that should be aligned with the overall goals of the company. It is also important to define a unique positioning in the market that will help you stand out from competitors and attract your target audience.
Market and consumer research:	Marketing strategy analysis includes studying the market and target audience. Market research will help you understand its size, structure, competitive landscape and trends. Consumer analysis will allow you to better understand their needs, preferences and behavior, which in turn will help develop effective marketing strategies.
Assessment of the competitive environment:	Marketing strategy analysis involves studying competitors and their strategies. This will allow you to identify their advantages and weaknesses, as well as determine your own competitive advantages and ways to improve. This will help you develop marketing strategies that will compete successfully in the market.
Development of marketing mixes:	Marketing strategy analysis will help determine the optimal marketing mix, including product, price, promotion and distribution. This includes selecting the right range of products or services, setting a competitive price, selecting effective distribution channels and developing communication strategies to achieve marketing strategy objectives.
Efficiency mark:	Analyzing your marketing strategy will help you evaluate its effectiveness and determine the necessary adjustments. You can use various marketing metrics and tools such as sales analysis, market shares, customer satisfaction and other indicators to measure the results and effectiveness of your marketing efforts.
Innovation and adaptation:	Analysis of marketing strategy allows you to identify new opportunities and trends in the market. This will help the company be more flexible and adapt to changing conditions, and develop innovative approaches and products to meet customer needs and gain a competitive advantage.

Analysis and result of the research.

In modern conditions of increased competition and dynamic changes in the market environment, the effective implementation of marketing strategies is becoming a key success factor for joint-stock companies.

German experience. German joint stock companies demonstrate high efficiency in applying consumer-oriented marketing strategies. Thus, the Siemens concern actively uses market segmentation according to behavioral and psychographic characteristics, which allows it to most accurately determine the needs of different customer groups and adapt the offer to their needs. The company is also successfully implementing digital tools such as Big Data and AI to personalize communications and increase loyalty.

UK experience. British public companies such as Rolls-Royce and Unilever demonstrate high flexibility in marketing strategies. They actively use agile approaches to quickly test new ideas and quickly respond to market changes. In addition, companies pay great attention to the ESG agenda, integrating it into their marketing communications and brand positioning.

US experience. American public companies such as Apple and Coca-Cola are known for their innovative approach to the marketing mix. They actively use non-standard promotion channels, including social networks, affiliate programs and sponsorship activations.

Companies also use effective systems for analytics and evaluation of the effectiveness of marketing initiatives.

Chinese experience. Chinese publicly traded companies such as Alibaba and Tencent are highly adaptable to changing market needs. They actively use the integration of online and offline channels, and also develop ecosystem solutions to increase customer loyalty and retention.

Japanese experience. Japanese public companies such as Toyota and Sony are known for their systematic approach to managing marketing strategies. They closely integrate them with the company's development strategy, ensuring high consistency of all business processes. Companies are also paying great attention to upskilling marketing teams and developing their analytical competencies.

Conclusion.

The analysis of global experience in the use of marketing strategies by joint-stock companies demonstrates a number of key trends as: consumer focus, flexibility, an innovative approach to the marketing mix, the use of digital technologies and integration with the company's development strategy.

⁵Prepared by the author.

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